

FACIAL EXPRESSION RECOGNITION USING ATTENTIONAL NEURAL NETWORK**Nsangou Mouchili M.,***PhD, Assistant Lecturer, Department of Computer Engineering,
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National Higher Polytechnic Institute, University of Bamenda***ABSTRACT**

The development of models to predict human emotions has been inefficient due to limited accuracy and computational resources. The objective of this paper is to develop, implement, train, test, and deploy a more efficient model for facial expression recognition (FER). The FER 2013 dataset was used to train a proposed supervised machine learning model based on an attentional neural network, using different model hyperparameters. The model had the best performance when the precision, recall, and F-score were 70.45 percent, 80.08 percent, and 60.03 percent respectively. Analysis of experimental results demonstrates the competitive classification accuracy of our proposed method. Using this model, we created a simple application making use of a webcam to collect facial features, pre-processed the images using OpenCV, and made predictions. Based on the obtained results, we can conclude that we have successfully designed, implemented, trained, and deployed an efficient FER system using an attentional neural network.

Keywords: Facial Expression Recognition (FER), Attentional Neural Network (ANN), Supervised Machine Learning, F-Score, recall, precision, OpenCV, hyperparameters.

I. INTRODUCTION

Humans use different forms of communication such as speech, hand gestures, and emotions. Being able to understand one's emotions and encoded feelings is an important factor for an appropriate and correct understanding. Emotion recognition can be performed using different features such as face, speech, electroencephalogram (EEG), and even text. Among all these features, facial expressions are one of the most popular.

Although humans recognize facial expressions virtually without effort or delay, reliable expression recognition by machine systems is still a challenge. There have been several advances in the past years in terms of face detection, feature extraction mechanisms, and the techniques used for expression classification, but the development of an automated system that accomplishes this task is difficult.

In this paper, we propose an approach based on the Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) for facial expression recognition. Despite more than 20 years of extensive research and the large number of papers published in journals and conferences dedicated to this area, we still cannot claim that artificial systems can measure human performance regarding the face related challenges: difficult light imaging conditions, head pose, aging, facial expressions, variations in illumination, pose, alignment, and occlusions [1].

Face recognition is important for the interpretation of facial expressions in applications such as intelligent, man-machine interface and communication, intelligent visual surveillance, teleconference, and real-time animation from live motion images. Facial expressions are useful for efficient interaction. Most research and systems in Facial Expression Recognition (FER) are limited to six basic expressions (joy, sad, anger, disgust,

fear, surprise). It is found that it is insufficient to describe all facial expressions and these expressions are categorized based on facial actions.

Detecting the face and recognizing facial expressions is a very complicated task when it is vital to pay attention to primary components like face configuration, orientation, and location where the face is set. Using a face image without attention to the most critical regions introduces noise, increases the use of computational resources, reduces efficiency, and reduces the accuracy of the results. Therefore, no automatic systems are there that can track a person's activity. So, we decided to build a FER System.

In countries like Cameroon, the rate of crimes is increasing day by day. No automatic systems are there that can track a person's activity. If we can track the facial expressions of people automatically then we can find the criminals easily since facial expressions change while doing different activities. So, we decided to make a Facial Expression Recognition System. Therefore, the overall objective of this paper is to realize a very efficient and accurate facial expression system to predict emotions from a picture of a face. The specific objectives of the paper are:

- To develop a classifier for facial expression recognition.
- To experiment with machine learning algorithms in computer vision fields.
- To evaluate the accuracy of our FER system
- To deploy a FER system on a local computer using a webcam.

A. Significance of the work

This work improves the use of facial expression in a wide range of applications which can include Customer behavior analysis and advertising, healthcare, public safety, crime detection, robotics, employment, and provision of personalized services. In the field of security particularly, it can be used in lie detectors and smart border control. It can also be used to make predictive screening of public spaces to identify emotions triggering potential terrorism threats, and the analyzing footage from crime scenes to indicate potential motives in a crime.

B. Limitations of the work

This paper is limited to designing and training a model for predicting emotion from images or videos; it does not consider other properties such as vocal tune, behavior, and other factors that emotions can depend on. We are only concerned with the appearance of the face. In this work, we have not discussed other methods of detecting emotions like through sound or using other physiological methods like measuring heartbeat. An automatic FER system needs to solve the following problems: detection and location of faces in a cluttered scene, facial feature extraction, and facial expression classification.

C. Delimitations of the work

In this part of the section, we give a brief overview of the structure and content of this paper, which is divided into 4 main sections. Section I “Introduction” covers the introduction of the research paper where we explain the statement of the problem, motivation, and state the research hypothesis, objectives (general and specific), significance, limitations, and delimitations of the work.

Section II titled “Literature Review” covers face expression recognition using computer vision. We show how these various technologies can be applied in the context of our research paper. We also explore existing face expression recognition models and past re-

search methods and techniques used to address face expression recognition. We conclude by discussing some of the limitations of the models and techniques.

Section III, “Materials and Methods” covers the theory, methodology, and procedure followed to develop our FER system. We explore the various layers and units in convolutional neural networks and justify the layers we are going to use in our proposed algorithm. We also discuss the structure of the data we use to train our model. We explore the various frameworks and tools used to build, implement, and test our model.

Section IV, titled “Results and Discussion”, presents the model which has been built with the help of diagrams and screen captures of how the model works. We equally evaluate the performance of our model. Section V “Conclusions, Recommendation, and Perspectives” summarizes our research work, evaluates the developed model, and states recommendations for future work.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Caleanu and Bettadapura give a detailed overview of expression recognition [2]. In this section, the main work similar to the proposed method is presented as well as a few selected articles that give a broad overview of the different models. Recognizing facial expressions based on appearance has been an active research area for decades. Early methods relied on hand-crafted features such as Gabor Wavelets, Local Binary patterns on Three Orthogonal planes (LBP-TOP), Pyramid histogram of Oriented Gradients (PHOG), and Local Quantized Patterns (LQP) [3].

Lately, due to the great success of deep CNN in a wide variety of image classification tasks, it has also been applied in emotion recognition. One of the main attractiveness of deep CNNs is their ability to learn features directly from data, avoiding the tedious hand-crafted feature generation used in other supervised learning methods. The literature works share a standard structure and leads to a generic facial analysis system, which involves three basic steps as illustrated in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Generic architecture of an image-based FER system [1]

For face recognition, feature extraction can be performed globally or locally on the image. The obtained feature vector will be fed to the face classification step, which needs a training phase to make a classifier more capable of recognizing probe images. There are three classifier categories:

- 1) Similarity-based ones are known as the nearest neighbor rule.
- 2) Probabilistic approach using Bayes decision rule.
- 3) Decision boundary methods such as support vector machine SVM.

This new image classification architecture started emerging after 2010 with Deep CNNs' outstanding machine learning performance. The deep facial analysis relies on learning convolution weights and the decision ones (fully connected neurons) via backpropagation and loss-based optimization. Unlike handcrafted systems where the feature extraction and the classification

are disconnected, only the classifier is trained to get the maximum from the static extracted features.

Deep CNN learning considers mainly the earlier layers as they have a large learnable parameter set compared to the fully connected layers. Fig 2 illustrates the configuration of deep CNN-based image classification. There are three categories of feature computation: holistic, local, and learnable features.

Fig. 2. CNN-based architecture for facial expression recognition [1]

The literature experienced the proposal of many works devoted to enhancing the feature extraction process, resulting in an important number of techniques. ImageNet Large Scale Visual Recognition Challenge (ILSVRC) introduces GoogleNet [2], a deep neural network architecture that relies on CNNs. The proposed network has been evaluated on the Extended Cohn-Kanade Dataset and the MMI Dataset. The results of the experiments demonstrate the success of using a deep-layered neural network structure. A recognition accuracy of 99.6% has been achieved [4] with a 10-fold cross-validation.

Using the Extended Cohn-Kanade Dataset, Happy and Routray [5] classify between six basic emotions. The dimensionality of the features is reduced and then given to a Support Vector Machine. The average accuracy is 94.09%.

A deep convolutional neural network for learning facial expressions has been used by Song et al. [4]. Convolutional, pooling, local filter layers, and one fully connected layer are used to achieve an accuracy of 99.2% on the CKP set. The dropout method was used to avoid overfitting. Anderson et al. [4] have developed a face expression system, which can recognize the six basic emotions. This approach has been implemented

in EmotiChat. They achieve a recognition accuracy of 81.82%.

In 2013, an emotion recognition system using Robust Normalized Cross Correlation (NCC) was proposed by Zafar et al. [6]. This approach has been evaluated on different databases including AR FaceDB (85% Recognition Accuracy) and the Extended Cohn Kanade Database (100% Recognition Accuracy).

Most of the previous methods have considered the entire facial region as input information and have paid less attention to the sub-regions of human faces, which may lead to a large difference between the extracted and expected representations.

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

In this section, we discuss the different Layers of a CNN to have a full understanding of the underlying architecture. The Layers are the building blocks of every neural network and are components of our proposed architecture. We also discuss activation functions to identify the best for our architecture. We end this section by proposing our model which will be used in training our image dataset.

A. System Design

The system design shows the overall design of a system. In this section, we discuss in detail the design aspects of the system:

Fig. 3. System design

B. Phases in Facial Expression Recognition

The FER system is trained using a supervised learning approach in which it takes images of different facial expressions. The system includes the training and testing phase followed by image acquisition, face detection, image pre-processing, feature extraction, and classification. Face detection and feature extraction are carried out from face images and then classified into seven classes belonging to six basic expressions which are outlined below:

1) Image Acquisition - Images used for facial expression recognition are static images or image se-

quences. Images of faces can be captured using a camera. In this project, we used the FER 2013 generated by Google, a dataset provided by the Kaggle website, which consists of about 37,000 well-structured 48×48 -pixel grayscale images of faces. The images are processed in such a way that the faces are almost centered, and each face occupies about the same amount of space in each image. Each image must be categorized into one of the seven classes that express different facial emotions. These facial emotions have been categorized in the table below: In addition to the image class number (a number between 0 and 6), the

Table I

Face Expression Classes and Class Labels

Class Number	Class Label
0	Angry
1	Disgust
2	Fear
3	Happy
4	Sad
5	Surprise
6	Neutral

images are divided into three different sets which are training, validation, and test sets. There are about 29,000 training images, 4,000 validation images, and 4,000 images for testing. 2) The FER Dataset - The original FER data set was prepared by Pierre Luc Carrier and Aaron Courville by web crawling face images with emotion-related keywords. The images are filtered by human labelers, but the label accuracy is not very high.

3) Image Pre-processing - After reading the raw pixel data, we normalized them by subtracting the mean of the training images from each image including those in the validation and test sets. For data augmentation,

we produced mirrored images by flipping images in the training set at different angles during training.

4) Face detection - Face Detection is useful in detecting facial images. Face Detection is carried out in training datasets using a Haar classifier called Viola-Jones face detector and implemented through Opencv. Haar-like features encode the difference in average intensity in different parts of the image and consist of black-and-white connected rectangles in which the value of the feature is the difference of the sum of pixel values in black-and-white regions.

C. Proposed Architecture

We propose an end-to-end deep learning framework, based on attentional convolutional networks, to classify the underlying emotion in the face images. Oftentimes, improving a deep neural network relies on adding more layers/neurons, facilitating gradient flow in the network (e.g. by adding skip layers), or better regularizations (e.g. spectral normalization), especially for classification problems with many classes.

However, for facial expression recognition, due to the small number of classes, we show that using a convolutional network with less than 10 layers and atten-

tion (which is trained from scratch) can achieve promising results. Given a face image, it is clear that not all parts of the face are important in detecting a specific emotion, and in many cases, we only need to attend to the specific regions to get a sense of the underlying emotion. Based on this observation, we add an attention mechanism, through a spatial transformer network, into our framework to focus on important face regions. Fig. 4 illustrates the proposed model architecture. The feature extraction part consists of four convolutional layers, each two followed by a max-pooling layer and rectified linear unit (ReLU) activation function.

Fig. 4. Proposed architecture

They are then followed by a dropout layer and two fully connected layers. The spatial transformer (the localization network) consists of two convolution layers (each followed by max-pooling and ReLU), and two fully connected layers.

After regressing the transformation parameters, the input is transformed to the sampling grid $T(\theta)$ producing the warped data. The spatial transformer module essentially tries to focus on the most relevant part of the image, by estimating a sample over the attended region. One can use different transformations to warp the input to the output, here we used an affine transformation which is commonly used for many applications.

D. Materials

1) Anaconda 3 - Anaconda is the data science platform for data scientists, information communication professionals, and business leaders of tomorrow. It is a distribution of Python, R, etc. With more than 300 packages for data science, Anaconda [7] helps in simplified package management and deployment. Anaconda comes with a wide variety of tools to easily collect data from various sources using various machine learning and artificial intelligence algorithms. It helps in getting an easily manageable environment setup that can deploy any project with the click of a single button.

Fig. 5. Anaconda Navigator

The following packages were installed:

- OpenCV, a library that provides a wide variety of functions that can be used for processing images and other computer vision tasks [8]. This library has more than 2500 optimized algorithms, which includes a comprehensive set of both classic and state-of-the-art computer vision and machine learning algorithms.

- Pytorch; an open-source machine learning framework based on the Torch library, used for applications such as computer vision and natural language processing, primarily developed by Metal artificial intelligence.

2) Hardware tools - The computer used has the following specifications: HP EliteBook Folio 9480m Notebook; Intel® Core™ i5-4310U with Intel HD Graphics 4400 (2 GHz); Up to 3 GHz with Intel Turbo Boost Technology, 3 MB cache, 2 cores); 14" diagonal HD* anti-glare; Standard Viewing Angle; LED-backlit (1366 x 768); 1TB 7200 rpm SMART IV SATA II; 8GB DDR3L PC312800 SDRAM (1600 MHz).

3) Other tools - Apart from the major tools stated above, some other tools were also used to facilitate the development process of our system. These tools include VS Code integrated IDE, Spyder integrated IDLE, Microsoft Word 2019 for document editing, and Chrome and Microsoft Edge Web browsers.

E. System Testing

System testing was done by giving different training and testing datasets. This test was done to evaluate whether the system was predicting accurate results or not. During the phase of the development of the system, our system was tested time and again. The series of tests conducted are as follows:

- Unit Testing - In unit testing, we designed the whole system in a modularized pattern and each module was tested till we got the accurate output.

- Integration Testing - After constructing individual modules all the modules were merged and a complete system was made. Then the system was tested to determine whether the prediction given by the training dataset to the testing set was correct or not. After spending a couple of days on integration testing the average accuracy of our system was 70%.

F. System Evaluation

Evaluation of the system can be done using the following methods:

- Precision, assessing the predictive power of the algorithm.

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{(TP+FP)} \quad (1)$$

- Recall which is the percentage of correctly assigned expressions to the total number of expressions.

$$Recall = \frac{TP}{(TP+FN)} \quad (2)$$

- F-score which is a composite measure that benefits algorithms with higher sensitivity and challenges algorithms with higher specificity. The F-score is evenly balanced when $\beta = 1$. It favors precision when $\beta > 1$ and recalls otherwise.

$$F - Measure = \frac{(\beta^2+1) \times Precision \times Recall}{(\beta^2 \times Precision + Recall)} \quad (3)$$

All three measures distinguish the correct classification of labels within different classes.

We have then successfully implemented an attention-based ANN which takes as input a 48x48 face image and predicts the face expression based on seven different classes namely: fear, happy, angry surprise, neutral, sad, and disgust. The proposed model is better than

those discussed in Section II because of its fewer number of layers which prevents it from less accuracy caused by the gradient vanishing problem.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In this section, we will discuss the results of our findings based on our architecture discussed in Section III. We also presented the results of running a hyperparameter search, as well as evaluate the performance of our model. We will compare our model with some of the models and conclude by deploying this application to use a computer’s webcam. This research paper aimed

to develop a complete FER system. 2013 FER dataset was used for the experimentations. First of all, the system was trained using different random samples in each dataset by supervised learning. In each dataset, the data was partitioned into three parts for training, testing, and validation. Every dataset has completely different samples which are selected randomly in a uniform manner from the pool of the given dataset. We had to do parameter finding by running several instances with different learning rates, batch size, and number of epochs. The best hyperparameters are in the table.

Table II

Best Hyperparameters for Training				
Learning Rate	Epochs	Batch size	decay	Gamma
0.001	256	64	0.01	0.05

We also plotted the loss variation and the accuracy variation during training to find out how our model was learned.

The confusion matrix during testing is shown below. In the table, the row shows the actual classes, and the column shows the predicted classes.

Table III

Confusion Matrix							
Labels	Angry	Disgust	Fear	Happy	Neutral	Sad	Surprise
Angry	256	0	0	0	0	1	0
Disgust	1	182	0	0	0	0	0
Fear	2	1	219	0	0	0	1
Happy	25	40	173	98	1	19	0
Neutral	1	1	12	0	111	0	0
Sad	1	1	1	1	0	228	0
Surprise	12	15	141	1	0	11	60

The classifier made a total of 1619 predictions where the classifier predicted anger 300 times, disgust 239 times, fear 545 times, happiness 99 times, neutral 112 times, sad 259 times, and surprise 61 times. Whereas 260 cases were angry, 183 were disgusted,

223 were fearful, 356 were happy, 125 were neutral, 228 were sad and 240 were surprised.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This paper proposes an approach for recognizing the category of facial expressions. This paper’s objective was to

Fig. 6. Validation loss and Accuracy during training

develop a FER system implementing a computer vision and enhancing the advanced feature extraction and classification in face expression recognition, recognizing more facial expressions. The paper involves facial expression pre-processing of captured facial images followed by feature extraction using an ANN and classification of facial expressions based on the training of datasets of facial images.

To measure the performance of proposed algorithms and methods and check the results' accuracy, using the FER 2013 face database, the system has been evaluated using Precision, Recall, and F-score. The same datasets were used for both training and testing by dividing the datasets into training samples and testing samples in the ratio of 8:2. The Precision, Recall, and

F-score from the FER 2013 dataset were 70.45%, 80.08%, and 60.03% respectively.

Experiment results on the FER 2013 dataset show that our proposed method can achieve a good performance. The results demonstrated that deep CNNs are capable of learning facial characteristics and improving

facial emotion detection. Also, through the hybrid feature, we revealed that convolutional networks can intrinsically learn the key facial features by using only raw pixel data.

Figure 7 shows an example of our obtained outcomes.

Fig. 7. An example of the obtained results

We have successfully implemented an attention-based ANN that takes as input a 64x64 face image and predicts the face expression based on seven different classes namely: fear, happy, angry surprise, neutral, sad, and disgust. The proposed model is better than those discussed in section two because of its fewer number of layers which prevents it from less accuracy caused by the gradient vanishing problem.

We developed various ANNs for facial expression recognition problems and evaluated their performances using different post-processing and visualization techniques. The results demonstrated that deep ANNs are capable of learning facial characteristics and improving facial emotion detection.

Table IV

Results Comparison Table

Model	Number of layers	Accuracy	Recall	F-Score
GoogleNet [10]	22	65.20%		
VGG [11]	16	66.31%		
CNN [12]	28	62.44%		
ANN [9]	9	70.02		
ANN (this)	9	70.45%	80.08%	60.03%

The following table illustrates the above comparison. Our future work will focus then on improving the performance of the system and deriving more appropriate classifications which may be useful in many other real-world applications.

References

1. Kas, M. Development of handcrafted and deep-based methods, 2021.
2. Szegedy, W. L. (2014). "Going deeper with Convolutions." Retrieved from <http://arxiv.org/abs/1409.4842>.
3. Emad B, C. Z. (2016). Training Deep Networks for Facial Expression Recognition. One Microsoft Way, Redmond, WA 98052.
4. Peter B, F. T. (2016). DeXpression: Deep Convolutional Neural Network.
5. Routray, S. H. (2015). Automatic facial expression recognition using features of salient facial patches. *Affective Computing*, 1-12.
6. Kumawat, D. 7 Types of Activation Functions in Neural Network. Retrieved May 13, 2022.
7. Waseem, M. (2021, July 15). Python Anaconda Tutorial: Everything You Need To Know. edureka! Retrieved July 10, 2022, from <https://www.edureka.co/blog/python-anaconda-tutorial>.
8. Intel Corporation. (2021, September 9). Home page. Retrieved from OpenCV website: <https://opencv.org>.
9. M. Shervin, A. Amirali" Facial Expression Recognition Using Attentional Convolutional Network" *arXiv:1902.01019v1*, 2019.
10. R. T. Ionescu, M. Popescu, and C. Grozea, "Local Learning to Improve Bag of Visual Words Model for Facial Expression Recognition," *Work. Challenges Represent. Learn. ICML*, 2013.
11. M. I. Georgescu, R. T. Ionescu, and M. Popescu, "Local learning with deep and handcrafted features for facial expression recognition," *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, 2019, DOI: 10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2917266.
12. K. Liu, M. Zhang, and Z. Pan, "Facial Expression Recognition with CNN Ensemble," in *Proceedings – 2016 International Conference on Cyberworlds, CW*, 2016